

ENEOLI Wikibase: A collaborative working platform for the European Network on Lexical Innovation

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*European Network
on Lexical Innovation*

WIKIBASE

This talk: overview

- **ENEOLI COST action**
- **ENEOLI Wikibase**
 - Why Wikibase?
 - Contents
 - Collaborative workflows
- **Preliminary results**
 - Towards a knowledge graph of neology

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ENEOLI COST action

European Network on Lexical Innovation

- COST Action 22126, funded by the European Union
- Runs from October 2023 to October 2027
- A collaborative research network for sharing methodologies, tools and best practices in research on lexical innovation
- 4 Working Groups (WGs)
- 373 members from 50 countries
- Workshops, training schools, conferences, and joint publications
 - [Article in Lexikos 35 about ENEOLI](#)
 - Pre-conference workshop at Euralex 2026

- **WG1** *John Humbley, Ana Salgado*
 - Multilingual Glossary of Neology
- **WG2** *Ana Ostroški Anić, Federica Vezzani*
 - Methods, Digital Resources, and Tools

- **WG3** *Vincent Balnat, Kris Heylen*
 - Diachronic and Synchronic Comparative Studies
- **WG4** *Judit Freixa, Petar Božović*
 - Training in Neology

ENEOLI Wikibase Resources

- **NeoCorpus:** A bibliography and full text corpus, collaboratively compiled in a [Zotero group](#) and sent to our Wikibase (currently 1,418 items in Zotero)
- **NeoVoc:** A multilingual terminological resource for the domain of Neology ([see describing page](#))
- Descriptions of **neologisms** (see [modeling proposal](#))

- Wikibase, [free software](#), hosted on [Wikibase Cloud](#) (WMDE)
- ENEOLI Wikibase, online at <https://eneoli.wikibase.cloud>
- Currently, [65 users](#)

What is Zotero?

- A free and open source tool
- Collects research articles
 - article metadata
 - full texts
- Stores notes when working with articles
- Cites articles
- Produces bibliographies (citation styles)
- Citations in your texts (LibreOffice, MS Word, Google docs)
- Group libraries: collaborative editing

From Zotero to Wikibase

- Publication metadata is sent to Wikibase
 - Employed tools: [ZotWb](#), [OpenRefine](#)
 - Literal values for authorship (author names) and publication language (language names or codes) are linked to entities
 - The bibliography as Linked Data allows for advanced database queries, for example:
 - [Publication years and number of articles](#)
 - [Languages and number of articles](#)
 - [Bibliographical item types and number of articles](#)
 - [Authors and number of articles](#)
 - [Authors with Wikidata ID \(federated query\)](#)

Author reconciliation with OpenRefine and Wikidata

fullName_recon_Wikidata	fullName_recon_Wikibase
Anna B. Nikulásdóttir <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Create new item Search for match	Anna B. Patraşcu <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Create new item Search for match
Carina Nilstun Choose new match Carina Nilstun (Q63256230) philologist and lexicographer (*19...) Norwegian Academy	Mădălin-Ionel Patraşcu <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Create new item Search for match
Vitor Augusto <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Create new item Search for match	Isabel Pereira <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Isabel Amaral (100) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Isabel B Pereira (100) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Isabel Pereira (100) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Create new item See more Search for match
Magadán Oliv <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Create new item Search for match	Katya Pertsova <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Create new item Search for match
Marko Orešković <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Marko Orešković (100) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Marko Orešković (100) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Create new item Search for match	Mike Pham <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mike Pham (100) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mike Pham (100) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Create new item Search for match
Mehriban Orucova <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Create new item	David A. Pharies Choose new match
	Matthieu Diarce Choose new match

Match this cell Match all identical cells Cancel

 Isabel Pereira (Q85647514)
researcher (ORCID 0000-0002-9769-7208)

NeoVoc Concept entries

What does a concept entry include?

- **Glosses:** captures the essential distinctive features of the concept in each working language (disambiguation)
- **Equivalentents:** one or several equivalentents per language (terminological matches)
- **Semantic relations:** e.g., truncation is a type of reduction
- **Domain labels:** indicate disciplinary or thematic scope
- **Interoperability links:** connections to external resources (e.g., Wikidata, NeoCorpus)
- **Discussion page:** supports collaborative dialogue
- **Collaborative editing:** users contribute through structured properties (e.g., the validated by qualifier)

borrowing (Q1083)

process by which a word from one language is incorporated into another language
linguistic borrowing | lexical loan

▼ In more languages
Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	borrowing	process by which a word from one language is incorporated into another language	linguistic borrowing lexical loan

borrowing (Q1308)

a word taken from another language
loan | loanword

▼ In more languages
Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	borrowing	a word taken from another language	loan loanword
Portuguese	empréstimo	unidade que resulta do processo de transferência de uma unidade lexical de uma língua para outra ou de um registo linguístico para outro dentro da mesma língua	empréstimo lexical
French	emprunt	mot résultant du procédé par lequel une langue intègre directement un élément d'une autre langue	emprunt lexical
German	Lehnwort	Wort, das aus einer anderen Sprache in die entlehrende Sprache übernommen wurde	

NeoVoc Concept entries

Coverage (at the moment, nov. 18):

- **485** validated concepts
 - starting point: monolexical term in FR, from corpus
 - 2nd round: polylexical term in FR, from corpus
 - 3rd round: filling conceptual gaps: term in EN
- validated equivalents
 - **19** languages
 - **3681** equivalents
 - **2809** manually validated

https://eneoli.wikibase.cloud/wiki/NeoVoc#Coverage_of_NeoVoc_concepts_with_multilingual_equivalents

NeoVoc methodology

- **ENEOLI Task 1.1: Bottom-up approach**
 - Identify concepts by extracting (French) terms from specialised corpus (e.g. research articles, handbooks)
- **ENEOLI Task 1.3: Top-down approach**
 - Define concepts by constructing a concept scheme, based on Sablayrolles' matrix of lexical innovation processes
- **WG1 collab: 'Middle-out'** ([Uschold & Gruninger 1996](#))
 - Connect concepts from 1.1 and 1.3, find conceptual gaps
 - Terms identified in the corpus that do not correspond to any concept currently represented in the concept map
 - Concepts present in the scheme for which no matching terms appear in the corpus

Key issues:

- ❑ Does every lexical innovation *process* correspond to a lexical innovation *result* and vice versa?
 - ❑ [SPARQL queries at ENEOLI Wikibase](#)
- ❑ Are all *process* and all *result* concepts integrated in the hierarchy, i.e., are they declared subclass of another concept?
 - ❑ *2 root concepts: lexical innovation process, lexical innovation result*

Ongoing work on NeoVoc concepts

Process vs Result

- The mapping between lexical innovation processes and their results is not always clear-cut — e.g. *amalgamation* (process) vs *amalgame* (process + result), *borrowing* (process + result), *loanword* (result)

Other conceptual challenges

- Is a *blend* a kind of *construction*?
- Do *loanword* and *foreignism* refer to the same concept?

Key insight

- The conceptualisation of neology is language-dependent
- Different linguistic traditions not only use different terms, but also structure conceptual categories in distinct ways

Work on NeoVoc concepts

Wikibase enables collaborative editing of a living, versioned resource

- All edits are automatically tracked, ensuring transparency and allowing review
- Editing guidelines are available via wikitext pages within the same instance
- Language-dependent workflow descriptions and status queries
 - [all language pages](#)
 - example: [Greek page](#)
- equivalent [validation statistics](#)
 - validations per validator
 - validations per language

equivalent	<>> аффиксация (Russian) warning from Wikidata ▾ 0 references
	<>> affixation (English) validated by Michael Rosner linked lexeme sense ID L622-S1 ▾ 0 references
	<>> affixation (French) validated by ENEOLI panel of (French) experts linked lexeme sense ID L23-S1 ▾ 0 references
	<>> afixação (Portuguese) validated by Ana Salgado linked lexeme sense ID L273-S1

NeoVoc Lexical entries

NeoVoc includes lexical entries for validated equivalents

What does a lexical entry include?

- Annotations of any kind on **lexeme**, **sense**, and **forms** level
 - Grammatical features – POS, gender, number
 - Polysemy – each sense linked to a distinct concept
 - Word formation – affixation, blending, compounding
 - Etymology – when available
 - Frequency data – from NeoCorpus – linked to bibliographic records
 - Links to external resources – e.g. Wikidata lexemes
- **Discussion page:** supports collaborative dialogue

ENEOLI WIKIBASE

Navigation Wiki tools

[Lexeme](#) [Discussion](#)

(L157) **terminologie**
fr

Language French
Lexical category noun

Statements

instance of NeoVoc lexical entry
[0 references](#)

Senses

L157-S1 French branche de la linguistique étudiant les terminologies, les aspects du travail terminologique, les ressources terminologiques résultantes, et les données terminologiques

Statements about L157-S1

concept for this sense terminology
[0 references](#)

L157-S2 French ensemble de désignations et de concepts appartenant à un domaine ou sujet

Statements about L157-S2

concept for this sense terminology
[0 references](#)

NeoCorpus article indexation

1. PDF Zotero attachment is sent to the [GROBID](#) service
2. The cleaned text body is isolated as utf-8 TXT, and lemmatized using [SpaCy](#) (available [languages](#))
3. Terms from NeoVoc are found in the text (using [flashtext](#))
4. The Wikibase item describing the article is enriched with that information ([example](#))
 - Todo: stop list for every language (lexical units used in general lg.)
5. [Database queries](#) according to research question
 - What terms uses an author? Together with what other terms?
 - In what articles does a term occur? When were they published?
 - In a language, when started a concept-designating term to be used? - etc.

Neologisms descriptions

Lexical entries are created for neologisms to describe.

A lexical entry may include:

- A link to a lexical innovation process (NeoVoc concept)
- A link to a neologism type (NeoVoc concept)
- Links to source lexemes
- Linguistic description (category, gender...)
- Attestation quotes and references
- Sense: linked to an ontological concept

Work with tables (optional):

- Users can enter data in tables
 - controlled values
 - conversion to Wikibase-ID

Lexeme Discussion ★

(L1938) **gordofobia**
es

Language Spanish
Lexical category noun

Statements

part of collection	Task 3.6 Gender
▼ 0 references	
neologism type	hybrid compound
▼ 0 references	
lexical innovation process type	hybrid compounding
▼ 0 references	

ENEOLI Wikibase: becoming a Neology knowledge graph

- Authors
- Publications
- Meta-terminology
 - lexical entries
 - concept entries
- Neologisms
 - lexical entries
 - concept entries

Some SPARQL queries

- [NeoVoc lexical entries: occurrences in NeoCorpus articles](#)
- [Authors and the NeoVoc terms they use](#)
- [Authors, and in how many of their articles NeoVoc terms appear](#)
- [All articles that contain terms denoting one concept](#)
- [All concepts that appear in articles together with one certain concept](#)
- [Timeline of articles where a concept appears](#)

These are just some examples; depending on the research question, queries can be adapted or combined

Documentation, references

- ENEOLI Wikibase: <https://eneoli.wikibase.cloud>
 - user documentation and editing instructions, SPARQL example queries
 - scripts for upload and maintenance of NeoCorpus and NeoVoc [on GitHub](#)
- Wikibase in DH applications
 - See <https://dhwiki.wikibase.cloud> (DARIAH WG DHwiki)
- Lexical data on Wikibase
 - Lindemann 2025: "[Ontolex-Lemon on Wikidata and other Wikibase instances](#)"
- Terminological resources and Ontolex
 - Bosque et al. 2015: "[Applying the OntoLex Model to a Multilingual Terminological Resource](#)"
- Lexical innovation, neologisms classification
 - Sablayrolles 2019: "[Comprendre la néologie: conceptions, analyses, emplois](#)"
 - see also [ENEOLI Zotero group](#)

Questions?

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17583262>

Join our network!

ENEOLI European Network on Lexical Innovation

- <https://eneoli.eu>
- <https://www.cost.eu/actions/CA22126/>

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